

Understanding Christian Ethics in Line With Paul's Example in Local Churches in Rwanda

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Abstract: The Christian ministry is one ordained by God for a special purpose in His Kingdom (Exodus 40:12-15&John 15:16). It is the noblest work on earth and no any other profession can be compared to it. God calls us to walk humbly with Him. There may be no better model to emulate than Paul. In many ways, Paul became Christ's greatest apostle as he reached not only Jews but also much of the Gentile world. God was so pleased with Paul's ministry that he chose to set him as an example in the Scriptures of somebody to imitate (Corinthians 11:1). However, little is known about how present Christians in local churches can adopt and imitate Paul's model of Christian Ethics. The purpose of this study was to describe how present Christians in local churches understand Christian ethics to adopt it in line with Paul's example. The Study was a cross-sectional with qualitative approach. In-depth interviews and focus group interviews were used as research technique. Data was categorized to look for emerging themes then further distilled to identify any abstract themes that could be understood holistically. Evangelists, pastors and other Christian leaders were aware of Christian ethics and to some extent, they have tried to adopt it in line with Paul's example. Local church members were less aware of Christian ethics and did not attempt to imitate Paul's example of Christian ethics. The study findings showed that Christian leaders including pastors, evangelists, pastors understand more Christian ethics and have tried to adopt Paul's example than other church members. This study also suggests to put in place Christian education strategies that are adapted to local churches in order to reach out all Christian members that can adopt Paul's model of Christian ethics.

Key word: Christian, Christian ethics, Christian leaders, Ethics, Evangelist, Minister, Ministry, pastor.

I. Introduction

The Christian ministry is one ordained by God for a special purpose in His Kingdom (Exodus 40:12-15&John 15:16). It is the noblest work on earth and no any other profession can be compared to it. As stated in Jeremiah 23:4 and John 21:15-17, the work of a Christian minister aims at fostering the flock and leading them to win other lost souls to Christ. This is also definitely confirmed in John 4:24 and I Peter 1:16 that the work of a minister is spiritual and holy and leads in the warfare against the devil and his host of demons (Ephesians 6:12).The ministry consists of a family of people called by God for special service to Christ and His flock [1] and God calls us to walk humbly with Him. As far as ministry, there may be no better model to emulate than Paul [2]. In many ways, Paul became Christ's greatest apostle as he reached not only Jews but also much of the Gentile world. In fact, God was so pleased with Paul's ministry that he chose to set him as an example in the Scriptures of somebody to imitate. First Corinthians 11:1 says, "Follow my example, as I follow the example of Christ." Philippians 3:17 says, "Join with others in following my example, brothers, and take note of those who live according to the pattern we gave you." Paul is a model, and his ministry should be our constant study. We have detailed the characteristics of effective ministers by studying Paul's ministry to the Colossian church. We must be salt and light in our community; offering hope and a clear message of redemption through Jesus Christ.

II. Methods

This study was a cross sectional using qualitative approach with ontological and epistemological philosophy with subjectivism and interpretivism approach that enabled to have the details of the situation under study and understand the reality to be interpreted. In-depth individual interviews and focus group interviews were used as research technique. Data were categorized to look for emerging themes then further distilled to identify any abstract themes that could be understood holistically. The study enrolled 32 participants including 8 evangelists, 8 Christian leaders, 8 pastors and 8 Christian members of the local churches living in Kirehe District in eastern province of the republic of Rwanda. The study participants were selected randomly and the focus group discussion were used for each group that was invited to meet with researchers at the

place nearer with their working place. Each focus group discussion was composed with 8 persons. Before conducting interview, researchers explained the objective of the study and whoever agreed and accepted to be enrolled in the study has consented.

III. Results and Discussion

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Testimony of Christian leaders

During the interview, the evangelists said they understand well the Paul's model of Christian ethics, this is justified by the education background including biblical knowledge. They also tried to adopt Paul's model of Christian ethics and this might be due to fact that they wanted to be example of Christians they lead. Their view is summarized as follows:

" Paul's model of Christian ethics is very unusual, We understand Paul's model of Christian ethics as described in the Bible and we try to adopt it because we need also to be exemplary to our followers"

3.1.2. Testimony of Christian members

During the interview, Christian members said that they know what Christian ethics mean but they were not all aware of Paul's model of Christian's ethics. The lack of awareness can be averted by establishing Christian education program that is appropriate for local church members. Once, the program is established, local Christian members may be aware of the example of Paul and start to adopt it in their daily lives. The Christian members explained in the following way:

"We know what Christian ethics mean but all of us are not aware of the Paul's example of Christian ethics. We need some educational programs that can help learn Paul's example of Christian ethics. Once we understand the model, we can try it out"

3.2. Discussion

God instructs us to resist the temptation by looking for biblical ethical principles to guide our decision making [4]. These can be summed up in Matthew 22:37-40" *Love the*

Lord your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your mind.’ This is the first and greatest commandment. And the second is like it: ‘Love your neighbor as yourself.’ All the Law and the Prophets hang on these two commandments”. Cristian ethics basically originate from the Ten Commandments [5] and we should recognize that true Christian morality involves going beyond the mere letter of the law (Mt 5:21-22, 27-28) to the very spirit of love on which it is based (1Cor 13:4-8). The following principles are based on the Ten Commandments. The minister has to know the Sovereignty of God” We must put always put him first” as stated in *Exodus 20:3*. God has made us stewards of his creation and guardians of the planet (Gn 1:26, 28). This validates scientific enquiry and application but is not a license for exploitation, nor for seeing medicine rather than God as humankind’s savior [6]. It is clear we must always exercise our delegated authority for good, especially for the good of individual human beings. Furthermore we should do it according to God’s revealed standards of right and wrong. The end does not justify the means [7]. God always asks us to honor our father and our mother (Ex 20:12). God has established human authorities as his agents to serve and protect us and we should submit to them and not rebel against their authority (Rom 13:1-7). Most important among these is the family which is God’s provision for the protection, nurture and discipline of children (Dt 6:6, 7 ; Eph 6:1-4) and the stability of society as a whole. God has also stated that we shall not murder (Ex 20:13) due to the fact that all human life is made in God’s image (Gn 9:6, 7) and is worthy of the utmost respect from its beginning to end[8]. God tells us to *not commit adultery (Ex 20:14) since the marriage is a life-long, publicly recognized, heterosexual, monogamous relationship (Gn 2:24; Mt 19:4-6; Eph 5:31-33) and is representative of Christ’s own relationship with the church. God has also obliged us to not steal (Ex 20:15). God has blessed human beings materially in order that they may provide for their own needs and those of others (2 Cor 9:8). We should show respect for the property of others and seek to use what he has given us in accordance with his revealed will [9]. We shall not give false testimony (Ex 20:16) and we should ‘speak the truth in love’ (Eph 4:15) at all times, using our words to build others up rather than tearing them down. Lying through commission or omission runs counter to the nature of God himself (Nu 23:19) and leads to injustice [10]. We should be people of our word (Jas 5:12). We shall not covet... (Ex 20:17) and we should be grateful and content with what God*

gives us (Phil 4:11-12), not being driven by jealousy or desire for the possessions, relationships, gifts or honor of others [11]. Rather we should desire to do his will, to have his gifts to serve others (1Cor 12:31) and most of all to desire God himself (Ps 37:4), knowing that he will provide us with what we need. The local church should instill these bible ethical principles into its members, who in turn, will constantly use them to Love the Lord their God with all their heart and with all their soul and with all their mind.' and 'Love their neighbor as themselves as stated in Matthew 22:37-40".

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